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ARTEMIS User Needs Survey

VR-AR specialist

Digital Tools, Monitoring Practices, and Data Acquisition

Digital Tools or Technologies

Digital Tools or Technologies used to Monitor Performance,

Data collected in Real Time

Challenges in Working with data

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Data Types, Formats, and Interoperability Standards

Types of Data

Data Format

Standard or Protocols

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Data Accessibility, Sharing Practices, and Collaboration Platforms

Data Structure and Accessibility

Use of Collaborative Digital Platforms

Main Difficulties in Sharing Data

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VR-AR specialist
3D Modelling, Digital Simulations, and Integration of Digital Technologies

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Digital Twin Applications, Functional Expectations, and Future Adoption

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Cross-analysis insights

TECHNOLOGIES × DATA TYPES	3D models of artifacts or buildings	Photographic or digitized images	Audio and video materials (e.g., interviews, oral histories)	Historical texts or archival records	Sensor or environmental monitoring data (e.g., lighting, acoustics)	User or visitor interaction data (e.g., from previous exhibitions or applications)	Metadata describing heritage assets	I don't directly work with data
3D modeling software (e.g., Blender, 3ds Max, Maya)	12	9	7	6	2	2	2	0
Game engines or interactive environments (e.g., Unity, Unreal Engine)	12	9	7	6	2	2	2	0
Augmented Reality applications	8	6	4	3	3	3	2	0
Virtual Reality headsets and systems	10	7	5	4	3	3	2	0
Motion capture or gesture tracking devices	4	4	4	4	1	2	2	0
Photogrammetry tools	9	7	6	5	2	2	2	0
3D scanning tools (e.g., laser scanners, structured light)	3	2	1	1	1	1	1	0
Immersive storytelling or experience design platforms	6	6	6	6	3	3	4	0
I contribute conceptually or narratively but not to technical	1	1	0	1	0	0	1	0

TECHNOLOGIES × REAL-TIME DATA	Yes, regularly through connected systems or sensors	Sometimes, depending on the project	No, data is static or pre-recorded	I'm not sure / Not applicable
3D modeling software (e.g., Blender, 3ds Max, Maya)	0	2	9	1
Game engines or interactive environments (e.g., Unity, Unreal Engine)	0	2	9	1
Augmented Reality applications	1	2	6	1
Virtual Reality headsets and systems	1	2	7	1
Motion capture or gesture tracking devices	0	1	3	0
Photogrammetry tools	0	2	7	0
3D scanning tools (e.g., laser scanners, structured light)	0	1	2	0
Immersive storytelling or experience design platforms	1	3	5	0
I contribute conceptually or narratively but not to technical	0	1	0	1

MONITORING TOOLS × MONITORING CHALLENGES	Limited availability of high-quality or accurate source data	Difficulties in aligning 3D models with historical or scientific accuracy	Technical constraints of platforms or devices (e.g., performance, compatibility)	Lack of interoperability between data sources and tools	Time-consuming data preparation or cleaning processes	Difficulty accessing data from institutions or archives	I don't encounter major challenges
User interaction and behavior tracking tools	2	1	4	3	4	2	0
System performance monitoring for VR/AR applications	3	1	1	2	1	2	0
Feedback and analytics platforms	2	1	4	3	3	2	0
I do not use digital tools for monitoring	2	2	6	3	3	2	0

DATA TYPES × FORMATS	3D file formats or models (e.g., OBJ, STL, glTF, point clouds)	Game engine project files (e.g., Unity, Unreal)	Multimedia formats (e.g., JPEG, MP4, WAV)	Audio narration or spatial audio formats (e.g., binaural WAV, ambisonics)	Metadata or description files (e.g., JSON, XML, RDF)	Motion capture data (e.g., BVH, FBX)	Source code or interaction scripts (e.g., C#, JavaScript, Blueprint)
3D models of artifacts or buildings	9	9	7	0	3	0	1
Photographic or digitized images	6	7	6	0	1	0	0
Audio and video materials (e.g., interviews, oral histories)	4	6	6	0	1	0	0
Historical texts or archival records	4	5	6	0	2	0	0
Sensor or environmental monitoring data (e.g., lighting, acoustics)	2	1	2	0	2	0	1
User or visitor interaction data (e.g., from previous exhibitions or applications)	3	1	2	0	2	0	1
Metadata describing heritage assets	2	1	3	0	3	0	1
I don't directly work with data	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

COLLABORATIVE PLATFORMS × SHARING DIFFICULTIES	Compatibility issues between different software and file formats	Lack of clear standards for immersive heritage content	Legal or institutional restrictions on data sharing	Concerns about intellectual property and data misuse	Limited collaboration between technical and heritage professionals	I have no difficulties in collaboration or data sharing
Yes, platforms internal to my institution	1	1	0	1	1	1
Yes, external or open-source platforms (e.g., Sketchfab, YouTube)	3	5	3	5	6	1
No, but I'd be interested in using them	2	1	1	0	3	2
No, I don't see their usefulness	0	0	0	0	0	0

3D MODELS × INTEGRATION CHALLENGES	Resistance to adopting emerging technologies within institutions	Lack of staff training or technical expertise	Difficulty aligning immersive content with curatorial or interpretive goals	Limited compatibility with institutional infrastructure or databases	Budget or resource constraints	No major challenges
Yes, frequently	6	7	4	2	10	0
Yes, occasionally	1	3	1	2	3	1
No, but I would be interested	1	1	1	0	1	0
No, and I don't see the relevance for my work	0	0	0	0	0	0

3D MODELS × DIGITAL TWIN USE CASE	Enhancing interactive storytelling and educational content	Simulating environmental or structural changes over time	Integrating real-time data into immersive experiences	Visualizing conservation or restoration scenarios	Enabling collaboration between technical and heritage professionals	Supporting accessibility and inclusive design	I don't see relevant applications
Yes, frequently	7	9	7	7	6	3	0
Yes, occasionally	2	2	2	1	1	2	0
No, but I would be interested	1	1	1	1	1	0	0
No, and I don't see the relevance for my work	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

SIMULATIONS × INTEGRATION CHALLENGES	Resistance to adopting emerging technologies within institutions	Lack of staff training or technical expertise	Difficulty aligning immersive content with curatorial or interpretive goals	Limited compatibility with institutional infrastructure or databases	Budget or resource constraints	No major challenges
Yes, frequently	2	2	2	1	3	0
Yes, occasionally	3	4	1	2	4	1
No, but I would be interested	2	4	2	1	6	0
No, and I don't see the relevance for my work	1	1	1	0	1	0

SIMULATIONS × REACTIVE DIGITAL TWIN SUPPORT	Real-time integration of environmental or usage data	Predictive simulations of material decay or environmental impact	Visualization of historical states and documentation	Interaction tracking and user behavior analytics	Scenarios for educational or interpretive adaptation	Alerts and notifications or status updates on changes to digital or physical assets	I'm not sure
Yes, frequently	1	2	2	1	2	1	0
Yes, occasionally	3	2	4	3	4	3	0
No, but I would be interested	3	1	4	3	3	2	1
No, and I don't see the relevance for my work	1	1	1	1	1	1	0